

RESEARCH ON SELECTION AND PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT OF BLAST HOLE DRILLING EQUIPMENT

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Abstract. *This paper describes the application of geological modeling-adapted sampling to improve operating costs and efficiency in some mining applications, and productivity in drill-and-blast processes. The objectives are to reduce the number of blast holes drilled and accidental access to the geologic boundary of interest. These goals come from an economic point of view, since the cost, firstly, is directly proportional to the number of drill holes, and secondly, it is related to the efficiency of recovery of the target material associated with excavation and blast damage. Therefore, problem formulation is an incentive to learn more about lithology and drill less. The main problem in creating an accurate surface model is that the sedimentary rock mass is usually coarsely sampled by drilling widely spaced exploratory holes. Thus, interpolation does not adequately capture local variations in the underlying geology. With the recent advent of consistent and reliable real-time detection of geologic boundaries in the field using borehole measurement data, we posed the problem of local model estimation in an adaptive sampling system. The proposed selection strategy consists of two steps. First, blast holes are drilled to the geologic boundary of interest and their locations are chosen adaptively to maximize benefit in terms of incremental improvements to the evolving spatial model. The second phase relies on forecast geology and conducts expert-driven drilling at a predetermined distance from the geological boundary of interest to optimize blasting and minimize its damage. Using data from the Kalmokir Study Bench in the Republic of Uzbekistan, we show that appropriate selection of blast holes in Stage 1 can reduce the total number of holes drilled into the top of the coal seam and optimize the blasting process, as opposed to random hole selection. we will show. maintaining a reasonable compromise in the error in seam-to-stop distances. We also show that adaptive sampling requires only a fraction of the holes initially opened for this data set for accurate estimation.*

Keywords: *Open pit blasting processes, charging explosives in a mine, detonators in mines, mine explosion limit, mine explosion sequence.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПО ВЫБОРУ И ПОВЫШЕНИЮ ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНОСТИ ОБОРУДОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ БУРЕНИЯ ВЗРЫВНЫХ СКВАЖИН

Аннотация. *В этой статье описывается применение адаптированного к геологическому моделированию отбора проб для повышения эксплуатационных расходов и эффективности в некоторых областях добычи полезных ископаемых, а также производительности в процессах бурения и взрывных работ. Цели состоят в том, чтобы*

сократить количество пробуренных взрывных скважин и случайный доступ к интересующей геологической границе. Эти цели преследуются с экономической точки зрения, поскольку стоимость, во-первых, прямо пропорциональна количеству пробуренных скважин, а во-вторых, она связана с эффективностью извлечения целевого материала, связанного с земляными работами и повреждениями от взрыва. Таким образом, постановка задачи является стимулом больше узнавать о литологии и меньше бурить. Основная проблема при создании точной модели поверхности заключается в том, что из массива осадочных пород обычно отбираются грубые пробы путем бурения разведочных скважин на большом расстоянии друг от друга. Таким образом, интерполяция неадекватно отражает локальные изменения в лежащей в основе геологии. С недавним появлением последовательного и надежного определения геологических границ в полевых условиях в режиме реального времени с использованием данных скважинных измерений мы поставили задачу оценки локальной модели в адаптивной системе отбора проб. Предлагаемая стратегия отбора состоит из двух этапов. Во-первых, взрывные скважины бурятся до интересующей геологической границы, и их местоположение выбирается адаптивно, чтобы максимизировать выгоду с точки зрения постепенных улучшений развивающейся пространственной модели. Второй этап основан на прогнозируемой геологии и предусматривает бурение под руководством эксперта на заданном расстоянии от интересующей геологической границы для оптимизации взрывных работ и минимизации их ущерба. Используя данные исследовательского стенда в Калмокире в Республике Узбекистан, мы показываем, что правильный выбор шпуров на этапе 1 может сократить общее количество скважин, пробуренных в верхней части угольного пласта, и оптимизировать процесс взрывных работ, в отличие от случайного выбора скважин. Мы покажем, поддержание разумного компромисса в погрешности расстояний от шва до упора. Мы также показываем, что для точной оценки адаптивной выборки требуется лишь часть отверстий, первоначально открытых для этого набора данных.

Ключевые слова: процессы взрывания открытым способом, загрузка взрывчатых веществ в шахту, детонаторы в шахтах, предел взрываемости шахты, последовательность взрывов шахты.

Introduction

Drilling of blasting process wells in mining enterprises means mining with drilling equipment small pieces of mining rock formed as a result of exposure to rock and drilling is meant to bring up. The effectiveness of drilling wells is many depends on factors, the main of which is the drillability and fracturing of the mining rocks is considered Drillability of the rock is the drilling of the rock is a property of distortion under the influence of the instrument. With the drillability of mining rocks technological indicators of drilling rigs are selected accordingly. Mining is the process of preparing ore for mining to change the natural state of the mining rock in order to ensure its effectiveness involves a directed process. Hard rock on the step in preparation for rock mining blasting, and rocks of moderate hardness broken down mechanically. Grinding by mechanical method to grinding by blasting method It is more useful because of its high productivity, low cost and practicality safety is high. Coefficient of resistance to crushing by mechanical method can be applied to rocks up to $f=8$. In open-pit mining enterprises, the charge

of explosives is mainly extended construction is used, and the charges in this construction are as follows has achievements:

- a) Drilling works performed to place the charge relatively small size.
- b) Charging works require less labor;
- c) Uniform distribution of the charge in the array.

Picture 1. Illustration of hole blasting design and layout of charging scheme in blasting moderately hard rocks in Kalmakir mine.

Until recently, the open pits were mostly filled with flat columns charges were applied. Mining rock massif with a charge in such a structure large amount of oversize formation at the top of the step when blasting along with excessive crushing of mine rocks near the charge was observed to leave. In this case, when the charge is detonated, it has a large volume near it very finely ground rocks are formed. The main reason for this high pressure of gaseous products of the explosion in the chamber where the charge is located spread under. Such unevenness of the mine rocks after the explosion crushing causes problems in working with them. The formation of an air cavity in the wellbore gives the character of the explosion in a solid environment causes a change: the density of the explosion pressure is noticeably reduced, the rock around the charge is prevented from being too crushed, the time of active impact of the explosion on the mine rock array is extended, the charge of voltage waves generated by the explosion of the lower and upper parts interference is observed. In this case, the air gap is the beginning of the explosion acts as a compensator that reduces the pressure generated during charge chamber due to such a change in the indicators of the explosion pulse excessive grinding of the surrounding mining rocks is reduced, i.e the energy released in the explosion has a uniform effect on the rock mass of the mine shows. This conclusion is an experiment conducted in various con-geological conditions confirmed in his works. Thus the air is divided by space when the charges are detonated, as a result of the intersection of the voltage waves generated from the top and bottom of the charge, the mine rock massif it is inevitable that the level of grinding will be good and uniform.

Picture 2. Mine blasting design and explosion sequence in charging.

Republic of Uzbekistan the construction of well charges in the Kalmakir field is without air gaps charging of wells with an explosive substance is a special charging is carried out mechanized with the help of machines. In this case, the block is prepared by drilling before starting the charging operations after the calculations were carried out and the blasting order was issued then charging is done. Blasting site an engineer-technical employee performs blasting at the beginning of each shift prepared by drilling employees and drivers of charging machines charging a series of wells in the block and preparing them for blasting along with introducing all the documents about blasting instructions for safe implementation. Explosive substance blasting block mine foreman or blasting employee under the supervision of the charging machine is brought and charging works is done. The route of movement of the charging machine is the mine master or shall be shown by the blasting employee. After the charging vehicle is driven onto the charging well the blaster prepares it for charging. In this case, the blasting employee is a charging machine lowering the hoses into the well and driving the mixing chamber driver reports the launch. 1200 by the driver after that the driver is started by the operator at the frequency of rpm the remote control for determining the mass of the explosive substance is monitored (in this case, the driver the mass of the explosive substance is determined depending on the number of revolutions of the fixed screw). Operator as directed by blasting officer the auger is started by Charge mass meter indicator being sent to the well is controlled by Remote control device for charging using and designed to work in automatic mode. After the wells are charged to a certain height, they carry out blasting operations the employee drops a warhead into the well and then the well an explosive charge is poured into the remaining part. If the water level in the well is up to 0.5 m, the well Emulgit-30 if more than 0.5 m with explosive Emulgit-60 explosive charged with In this case, the height of the water level in the well is more than 0.5 m when the hose is lowered below the water level, then charging works is done. After the charging machine runs out of explosives from the charging unit of the blasting head blasting machine allows him to leave. If in the charging machine

after the completion of charging in the block if the explosive remains, it is installed according to the instructions returned to the warehouse in order. At the end of the shift, the driver-operators charge the machine in a special place augers and bunkers are washed and cleaned with water. Weather in the winter season when the temperature is below 0 C, these works are carried out using compressed air is increased. As we know, methods of detonating explosive charges are per charge depending on the source of the initial impulse, it can be carried out with the help of a flame, electric, electrolytic and detonation plug. Kalmakir In the quarry, the detonation plug included in the SINV system is used done.

Conclusions

It was determined that each pre-separated blast holes should be and the blasted zone is demarcated before drilling adjacent production blast holes. Explosives were fired along with pre-detonated blast holes, and that's it we think that it is not giving good results. Cracks were also found outside a row is placed along the pre-allocated line. The distance between the pre-separated holes was 1.2 m optimal for a drill diameter of 85 mm for a bench height 10 m and 12 m. Based on the results before the required division according to the formation of the rocks. The results of the explosion vibration study confirmed that reduction in vibration level was up to 30% due to pre-splitting. These results also confirmed that the pre-separation works as a filter and we can observe the attenuation of the vibration. A number of experiments were conducted. Exploding with explosive wires to open holes and it will be necessary to transmit a pre-allocated detonation signal. Pre-separated holes were fired with an explosive cord gave better results than those working with pipes. Pre-split the blast results also confirmed the mouths of the pre-split holes. 2 m should be left open without explosives to get the required pre-spliced line. Rock blasting distances vary in length and depth. Mine explosions are detonated with an electronic delay mass of rock detonators helped to achieve the desired blasting results in geological faults formation because there was better control over the delay intervals and the distance between the holes in the blasting round will need to be taken into account. A mass of broken rock near the cracks, the shear wire was further strengthened with bolts and after cleaning the loose stone, a wire mesh is formed. This is planned design the fire of the high-rise benches like this minimum throwing of blasted mud is done on lower benches and. In the mine accordingly, the firing of the upper benches was raised from the center, i.e. the benches were fired across the shot in a blasting sequence instead of being fired in parallel rows on top of the rows. Holes are located nearby the bench top is provided with 54ms hop delays. This consists of the middle of the central lifting face and the adjacent start, row holes are blasted against the center row.

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